

A Comparative Study of Characters and Themes of Two Short Stories “The Open Window” and “The Storyteller” by Hector H. Munro (Saki)

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Abstract

In this research, Edwardian satirist Hector Hugh Munro’s “The Open Window” and “The Storyteller” are selected for the analysis. This research is done with the aim of conducting a comparative study of the characters and themes found in the two stories. The objectives of this paper are to analyze the characters and themes in the two stories to find the similarities and differences of characters and of themes between the two stories. Characters are analyzed using Bergman’s theory and themes are analyzed using Perrine’s principles. From the analysis, it is found that Vera, the protagonist from “The Open Window” and the bachelor from “The Storyteller” are amazingly similar with only one difference: the bachelor is not a manipulator like Vera. Although the main theme of the two stories are different as the theme of “The Storyteller” is “the hollowness of the elaborated Edwardian conventions and extravagant and ostentatious lifestyle” while that of “the open window” is “the inadequacy of didacticism”, they have similar sub-themes which is “the faultiness of people perception that old people are always wiser than younger ones”.

1. Introduction

Hector Hugh Munro (1879 - 1916) was a British writer who wrote columns and short stories under the pen name “Saki”. A prominent satirist he is, most of his stories are remembered for the display of mischievous sense of humor. His stories give readers a sudden force that highlights the follies and vice of man. Saki was outstanding in attacking the hypocrisies and shortcomings of human beings. He is sometimes compared to O.Henery as his stories also contain surprise ending or “twists”.

1.1. Background to the study

People read literature for various reasons. Generally, literature is a means of communication among people. Literature can arguably also be used to promote a person’s language skills. Carter et al (1991) provided three reasons why literature is important for EFL students. The first reason is that literature expresses the most significant ideas and sentiments of human beings and teaching literature represents a means by which students can be put in touch with a range of expression often of universal value and validity over a historical period or periods. Teaching literature within such cultural orientation enables students to understand and appreciate cultures and ideologies different from their own in time and space and to come to perceive tradition of thought, feelings and artistic form within the heritage the literature of such cultures endows. The second reason is that the teaching of literature can promote language development. However this does not mean to teach literature with the sole purpose of teaching specific vocabulary or structures. Instead, by putting the students in touch with some of the more subtle and varied creative uses of the language, such exposure of literature can provide students with language development. The final reason why literature is beneficial for EFL students is that, by engaging with the reading of literary texts, it helps students to grow as individuals as well as in the relationship with the people and institutions around them.

The above reasons clearly explain why English language learners should study literature. And the study of literature starts with a literary analysis. Literary analysis means a

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careful examination and sometimes evaluation of a work of literature or an aspect of a work of literature and explaining the different elements of a piece of literature.

In the two short stories selected for this research, the researcher finds that the technique of embedding stories within stories and the two protagonists interesting as the two stories share many similarities. It is for this reason that the researcher make a comparative study of characters and of themes from the two stories to find out the similarities and differences to enable EFL students to have better comprehension of the two particular works of Saki.

1. 1. 1. Historical background

Most of Saki's stories are usually set in Edwardian England. This era is named after King Edward VII (1841 - 1910). He was the eldest son of Queen Victoria and Prince Albert. Wycoff (2013) stated that it is rather difficult to constrain any period in history to a strict standard of years. Therefore, some claim that Edwardian era starts from 1901 - 1910 while for some 1901 - 1919, the year that saw the signing of the Treaty of Versailles. For others Edwardian era stretches from the mid 1890s to the outbreak of World War I in 1914.

Kufnerova (2012) in her research "The Image of Women in Saki's Short Prose" quoted Hynes (1968) that the Edwardian period is often perceived as a romantic Golden age:

It is easy to feel nostalgia for that leisure time,....., and the sun really never set on the British flag. Writers on Edwardian England are inclined to call the time "golden".....(Hynes, 1968)

Edwardian era followed Victorian era adopting most of its values and ideas. Generally, Victorian England was characterized by the strong imperialistic features, class division and strict morals (Kufnerova, 2012). Unlike the previous era, Edwardian era witnessed the people of different classes mixed more freely (Weisser et al 2008). Moreover, due to the amount of social changes it started, it represents the transitional period between traditional Victorian England and modern twentieth century state (Kufnerova, 2012).

Nonetheless, Edwardian England was still dominated by aristocrats as "the nobility's lavish spending, carefree lifestyle, and personal behaviour that flaunted the morals of the times were chronicled in weekly magazines....." (Weisser et al, 2008)

For the Edwardian High Society, "wealth, birth and manners were the prime qualifications for commanding respect and obedience from others. High society resembled a club, not a caste, and the image was reinforced by a laborious set of rules and formalities which served to emphasize the distance between those in Society and those not in Society. Those who deviated from the expected behavior.....almost socially extinct" (www.fashion-era.com).

Therefore, Hynes (1968), cited in Kufnerova (2012)'s research, pointed out that the Edwardian society was one where "the forms of values had become the values; institutions had become more important than the ideas they embodied.

1. 1. 2. Theoretical Background

Bergman (1988) puts forward that character is the person or thing that performs the actions of the story and every story has at least one character. Usually characters are people but they can be animals, robots, ghosts or natural phenomena such as storms, earthquakes and fires. Regarding the evaluation of character, he pointed out that usually characters are described. Readers are given information about their height, weight, hair, eyes, and clothing. Through the plot, we have a chance to observe the characters' behavior. Through dialogue, we learn what they have to say for themselves and what other characters say about them.

According to Bergman, there are two means of understanding characters. Readers will be told what happens in a character's mind, in his or her innermost, unexpressed thoughts and feelings by an omniscient narrator. At other times, readers will be given a great deal of concrete evidence by which we can form their own independent evaluation of the characters.

According to Perrine (1966) the theme of a short story is its controlling idea or its central insight. It is the unifying generalization about life stated or implied by the story. Sometimes the theme of a story is explicitly stated somewhere in the story, either by the author or by one of the characters. More often, the theme is implied I.e. the readers are given hints to discover for themselves.

He provided six principles that can guide a person in finding the theme of a work.

1. Theme must be expressible in the forms of a statement with a subject and a predicate. It is insufficient to say that the theme of a story is motherhood or loyalty to country. If we express the theme in the form of a phrase, the phrase must be convertible to sentence form, for instance, the theme "the futility of envy" can be converted into "envy is futile"
2. The theme must be stated as a generalization about life. There must not be in the form of a specific statement with the name of the characters from the story.
3. Theme must not be generalization larger than is justified by the terms of the story. Terms like "every, all, always, should be used very cautiously; terms like some, sometimes, may are often more accurate"
4. The main theme is the central concept of the story. Therefore,
 - (a) it must account for all the major details of the story. If the theme cannot be expressed with all the important incidents or characters in the story, then it is sub-theme.
 - (b) It must not be contradicted by any detail of the story.
 - (c) It must not rely on supposed facts- facts that are not stated or clearly implied by the story.
5. Theme of a story can be stated in more than one way.
6. Theme should not be reduced to some familiar saying such as "you can't judge a book by its cover" or a stitch in times saves nine" although such a statement may express the theme accurately.

1. 1. 2. 1. Definition of key terms

1. Protagonist: The central character in the story, whether he be a sympathetic or an unsympathetic person.
2. Antagonist: The forces that are in conflict with the protagonist. The antagonist may or may not be human.
3. Foil: A foil is a character who provides contrast to the main character (protagonist) in order to emphasize the main character's traits. A foil can be one of two types; (1) an opposite foil who is the opposite of the major character so the major's virtues and strengths become much "brighter" in reflection or (2) a complementary foil who is someone like the major character but with lighter versions of the major's virtues and strengths so that the major comes off as even stronger.
4. Round character: The character is complex and many-sided. He might require an essay for full analysis.

5. Flat characters: The character has only one or two traits and can be summed up in a single sentence.

6. Dynamic (or developing) characters: Dynamic characters change in the course of the action and often are changed by the very events and conflicts they encounter. He/she undergoes permanent (but not minor) change in some aspect of his character, personality or outlook. The change may be a large or a small one; it may be for better or for worse.

7. Static characters: static characters do not change during the course of a story. They remain the same sort of persons at the end of the story as he was at the beginning.

1. 2. Synopses of two short stories

Both “The open window” and the storyteller” are told in the frame of a story within a story.

1. 2. 1. The Open Window

Framton Nuttel was an old man suffering from nervous ailment. So he came to live in the rural area to take a complete rest and cure his illness. Mr. Nuttel’s sister gave him letters of introduction to all the people she knew there. So Mr. Nuttel paid a formal visit to Mrs. Sappleton, one of his sister’s friends when he arrived there. While he was waiting for Mrs. Sappleton to come down, Vera, her niece told him a tragedy. Vera was a very self-possessed young lady of fifteen. According to her story, Mrs. Sappleton kept opening the window every evening till dusk because she thought that her dead husband and her two young brothers together with their little brown spaniel would come back walking in through that window. When Mrs. Sappleton came down to meet Mr. Nuttel, she told him that she had opened the window as her husband and her brothers would be back from shooting coming through this window. Mrs. Sappleton seemed to be proud of her husband and her two brothers; she kept making remarks about shooting and the three gentlemen which only scared the poor old man. Mr. Nuttel was not successful in trying to change the subject by telling Mrs. Sappleton about his ailment. All of Mrs. Sappleton’s attentions were at the open window. Then when Mr. Nuttel saw her husband and brothers actually came home with their little dog, he fearfully dashed off without a word of goodbye. As Mrs. Sappleton and her husband were surprised at the old man’s strange behavior, Vera explained that it was because Mr. Nuttel was afraid of dogs and she introduced another story in which Mr. Nuttel was hunted by a pack of pariah dogs and had to hide in a newly dug grave all night. Romance at short notice was her specialty.

1. 2. 2. The Storyteller

Three children - a small girl, a smaller girl, a small boy named Cyril and their aunt were traveling in a train. In their carriage, there was another occupant, a bachelor. The aunt and the children did not talk much and all the aunt told the children was “don’t do this” or “don’t do that”. However, the aunt failed to control the three little children. There were making noises playing and singing. They asked questions which the aunt was unable to give satisfactory answers. So the aunt decided to tell them a story. Her story was about a good girl who made friends with every one because of her goodness. In her story, the little girl was finally saved from a mad bull by a number of rescuers who admired her moral character. The children did not enjoy her story. They all agreed that the story their aunt told them was “stupid”. The aunt’s unsuccessful communication with the children annoyed the bachelor. So the bachelor commented that she was not a good storyteller. His comment aroused the aunt’s anger, so she challenged him to tell them a story himself. The bachelor told the children a story that started with the same beginning. In his story, a little girl named Bertha was extraordinarily good. She won three medals for her goodness and she always wore them. The medals clinked against one

another as she walked. Bertha was such a good girl that the prince of the country allowed her to walk in his park. Bertha felt very proud to visit the prince's park. The bachelor's story ended with Bertha being eaten alive by an enormous wolf as the clink of her medals let the wolf know her hiding place. All three children agreed that it was a beautiful story. But the aunt detested the story and told him that his story was the most "improper story" to tell to young children. The bachelor retorted that he kept the children quiet for ten minutes which the aunt was unable to do. When the bachelor left the carriage, he was thinking that the children would be asking her in public to tell them improper story for the next six months.

2. Research Methodology

In this researcher, the characters and themes of Saki's two stories are analyzed using Bergman (1988)'s theory and Perrine (1966)'s principles. The research procedure is firstly characters from the two stories are chosen to analyze. There are altogether twelve characters in two stories; seven in "The Open Window" and five in "The Storyteller". Among them, only protagonists and antagonists were selected for analysis. They are Vera, the bachelor, Mr. Framton Nuttel and the aunt. After they are selected, they are analyzed using Berman (1988)'s theory to find out the similarities and differences. Next, the themes of the two stories are analyzed using Perrine(1966)'s principles to investigate the similarities and differences.

3. Analysis of characters

There are altogether twelve characters in two stories.

3.1. "The Open Window"

There are altogether seven characters in the story as follows.

No.	Character's name	Characters role
1.	Vera	Major character (Protagonist)
2.	Mr. Framton Nuttel	Minor character (Antagonist)
3.	Nuttel's sister	Minor character
4.	Mrs.Sappleton	Minor character
5.	Mr. Sappleton	Minor character
6.	Mrs. Sappleton's two young brothers	Minor characters

3.1.1. Vera (The protagonist)

Vera is apparently the only young female in a well-off upper-class family in the story. She is a static character who manipulates people from the start to the end of the story. Her name is ironic because the name "Vera" means "the truth teller". the name "Vera" derives from the Latin word "Verax" which means "truthful" (www.babynamewizard.com). So it is ironic to learn that she tells lies while her name suggests that she tells the truth. It is her manipulative personality that is in conflict with that of naive Framton. This is the central conflict that the whole story revolves around. The readers are not informed that Vera is making a fool out of the old man until the last part of the story.

Firstly, Vera is mischievous. She scares off the nervous old man with her lies and fools her family members for her won amusement although she does not seem to have any bad intentions.

However, her mischievousness makes her appear immoral and rebellious if one considers the time period the character is set to live in. The story is set in Edwardian England. It was the time people within this society respected norms and rules of social etiquette as they desired to be civilized people. For Edwardians, good morals and good manners were the most important. Moreover, in an era where women were supposed to be “as delicate as a flower” and expected to become a perfect hostess in the future when she marries (Kufnerova, 2012), Vera does not submit to the society’s convention: she tells lies and she lies to older people. This shows she is not only immoral but also rebellious.

Nevertheless, Vera is a strong character with strong personality. Her immorality and rebellion reveals that she is an independent thinker. She does not let the conventions, traditions and values of her time and society govern her.

Vera is very witty intelligent. After talking to gullible Mr. Nuttel for a few seconds, she learns that Mr. Nuttel knows nothing about her town’s people. So she decides to take advantages of Mr. Nuttel’s lack of information about the area and its people. She sets her story at a time when Mr. Nuttel’s sister has moved to another place which is exactly three years ago as she knows that Nuttel has a sister who lived in the region four years ago. Again, we can infer that Vera knows beforehand that her aunt’s husband and two young brothers went out shooting and they would come in through that door. So she uses “the open window” as a symbol of a window’s grief and expectation to give eeriness. And again she must have noticed that her aunt is a typical Edwardian woman who wants to be a perfect hostess and who takes pride in the men in her family. So she chooses the three gentlemen as protagonists of her story for she knows that her aunt will talk about them and the shooting related topics. Vera is so witty and intelligent that she manages to tell amazingly convincing and interesting stories.

Vera is very **imaginative and creative**. She sets her second story somewhere on the banks of the Ganges instead of just a town in India to give her audience the excitement and the adventurous spirits. Her imagination leads her to choose the place of her story to be a cemetery and the antagonists a pack of pariah dogs. And she does not let the protagonist of her story go home without spending the night in a newly dug grave.

She is a **good storyteller**. She knows the language she should use to give the effect that she wants her story to have. She knows how to make use of literary devices. She intentionally says the following sentences to make a foreshadowing:

“Then you knew practically nothing about my aunt?”

“You may wonder why we keep that window wide open on an October afternoon,”

“That was the dreadful part of it”

“Do you know sometimes on still, quiet evenings like this, I almost get a creepy feeling that they will all walk in through that window...”

She is a master of words. She says

“Her great tragedy..” instead of “tragedy”

“.....window wide open on an October afternoon” instead of “....window open on...”

She uses imagery to create ghostly atmosphere.

“.....a *treacherous* piece of bog” instead of “ a piece of bog”

“..... a little *brown spaniel*” instead of “a little dog”

“.....a *white waterproof coat*” instead of “a mackintosh”

Vera is also a very clever and intelligent manipulator. A psychology author Simon (1966) outlines the following factors that primarily involve a manipulator. In a successful psychological manipulation, a manipulator.

1. conceals aggressive intentions and behaviors.
2. Knows the psychological vulnerabilities of the victim to determine what tactics are likely to be the most effective
3. Has a sufficient level of ruthlessness to have no qualms about causing harm to the victim if necessary. (www.wikipedia.com)

In the story, she plays an innocent young lady of fifteen in front of everyone. But she instantly knows Mr. Nuttel is a nervous type of man from his behaviors. She must have noticed the inner conflicts that Nuttel is facing. Therefore, as soon as she knows what type of man Nuttel is , she starts manipulating the old man saying “Then you know practically nothing about my aunt?” With this sentence, she is not only hinting at something eerie about her aunt, she is also making sure the type of man Framton is. Gullible as she predicts him to be, Mr. Nuttel replies “only her name and address”

The manipulative technique Vera uses is simple: lying. She is lying to Mr. Nuttel to his face. In her mind, she might be laughing at the poor old man believing everything she says. She is telling him lies the whole time. But she shows no sorrow or remorse for a man being used for her own amusement. She does not even give attention to the fact that Nuttel is already suffering enough of his own ailment.

Although Vera is a flat and static character with no personal development and growth in the story, she is a realistic character with interesting personality. She is mischievous and her mischievousness makes her appear rebellious and immoral. However, she has many qualities at the same time. She is witty, intelligent, creative and imaginative. She has strong personality; she is individualistic with her own opinions, very self-possessed and self-assured. Moreover, she is a good storyteller and a good manipulator. Therefore, when people read “the Open Window”, Vera is a character that demands their attention as she is unconventionally amusing and possesses remarkable personality.

3. 1. 2. Framton Nuttel (The antagonist)

The antagonist in “The Open Window”, Framton Nuttel is an old man who is suffering from nervous ailment. He is a flat and static character as he displays no personal growth or change throughout the story. He is a foil as his gullible personality is the direct opposite of Vera’s self-possessive personality.

In the story story, Mr, Nuttel moves to the rural area to cure his nerve. The fact that he could move to the country side means that he is rich because during Edwardian era only rich people can live in the country. Mr. Nuttel is the type of man who would like to be a part of a polite society where institutions, norms and customs were ranked first. This is evident where one looks at his words and actions. He is polite and respects the rules and conventions of his time; he carries letters of introduction, he pays formal visits, he wants to correctly flatter both the aunt and the niece. These facts prove that he hopes to be a perfect Edwardian whose dream

is to become a civilized man living in a polite society. So he is a symbol of Edwardian aristocrats.

He is used by Vera for her own amusement because he is credulous and socially awkward. In other words, Mr. Nuttel is psychologically manipulated by Vera because of his personality. The type of personality he has is like a magnet which will attract a manipulator. He will always be on the radar of someone like Vera.

Psychological manipulation is a type of social influence that aims to change the perceptions or behaviour of others through underhanded, deceptive or even abusive tactics. Martin Kentor describes “vulnerabilities” that a manipulator exploits in his book “The psychopath of everyday life: how antisocial personality disorder affects all of us” published in 2006 (www.wikipedia.com). Some of them are as follows.

The victims are

1. Too naive
2. Too trusting
3. Too lonely
4. Too dependent

Mr. Nuttel is too naive. He does not seem to expect Vera to be a liar. Even a single thought of doubt does not come into his head. He is too trusting. He does not even check for the credibility of the story. For example;

“an indefinable something about the room seemed to suggest masculine habitation.”

He should have looked for any evidence to support his instinctive feeling. Or at least he should have asked himself a question “why is this girl telling me, a stranger about an unpleasant experience of her own aunt?” “ But instead the old man trusts Vera and believes everything she says.

While he believes Vera, the old man seems to forget to trust himself and what his instincts are telling him. This describes that he has low self-confidence as he chooses not to trust what he sees and feels. Simon (1996) added that low self-confidence is also a major vulnerability in victims (www.wikipedia.com).

Poor old Nuttel’s low self-confidence is also the cause of his internal conflicts. Mr. Nuttel wants to say “correct something” to flatter the niece “without discounting the aunt”. He also doubts that his formal visits to strangers “would do much towards helping the nerve cure which he was supposed to be undergoing”. It seems that Mr. Nuttel regrets that he listens to his sister’s word to pay visits to some of the town’s folks as he answers Vera’s questions with “ a tone of distinct regret”

Another weakness that makes him a victim of manipulation is that he is too lonely as Mr. Nuttel is not used to making friends occasionally. This is evident when one looks at the words that describe his inner thoughts as well as those his sister says.

“Privately he doubted more than ever.....”

“I know how it will be” ”you will bury yourself down there and not speak to a living soul and”

Perhaps his state of being alone is he root for his social awkwardness or the other way around. But it is certain that Mr. Nuttel does not have a wide social network. So when he goes to Mrs.Sapleton’s house he is hoping for the family to be nice people.

Mr. Nuttel is also too dependent. Dependent people are always trying to please other people. They do not have the ability to disagree in the fear of losing support or approval. They are the type of people who would not take the responsibility of making a decision. And they are willing to place the demands of the people they depend on above their own. These are some of the characteristics of dependent people (www.webmd.com). Mr. Nuttel can be said as a dependent man because he does not make a decision himself. He goes to the houses to pay formal visits just as his sister told him to. But then he doubts whether this could does him any good. He does not seem to have the desire to socialize but then again because of his sister's demand, he agrees to do so. Mr.Nuttel seems like a pleaser too. One witnesses this when he tries to please both the aunt and the niece in the right way.

Nuttel is a nervous old man whose hopes are all unmet in the story. He moves to the countryside expecting nerve cure. He hopes to meet nice people. But at the end of the story, his nervous conditions are highly disturbed and people he meets are a liar who intentionally fooled him, a self-absorbed lady who thinks he is a boring old man and the three men who he thinks are ghosts. Therefore, in the story, he appears to be very ridiculous. It is his gullible personality that makes him a perfect victim for a manipulator. He is a flat and static character whose nervous behavior gives the readers endless amusement.

3. 2. "The Storyteller"

In the story, there are five characters in the story as follows.

No.	Character's name	Character's role
1.	The bachelor	Major character(protagonist)
2.	The aunt	Major character (Antagonist)
3.	The three children	Minor characters

3. 2. 1. The bachelor (The protagonist)

The bachelor is the protagonist in the story. He is a flat and static character. However, he has an interesting personality. Moreover, he possesses many qualities that make him a fascinating character.

The most prominent characteristic of the bachelor is that he is mischievous. He offends the aunt in front of her own nieces and nephew and tells a story of extraordinarily good Bertha being eaten alive by a wolf. At the end of the story, the bachelor thinks to himself that for the next six months the children will be asking the aunt "in public" to tell "improper story". This shows his darker side or his mischievous side for he knows what kind of story he has told the children and he purposefully tells "the improper story". But he does not show any malicious intention in the story. He does not intend to destroy the morals of children by telling them not to be good. Instead he simply warns the children that one's pride can be his own downfall while entertaining them with his unconventional story.

For Edwardian society, a civilized man of a polite society should have good morals and treating ladies with respect is one of them. Even at a dining room, a well mannered man must not seat himself until all the ladies at the table are seated. (Wycoff, 2013). For the age where such rules and manners are considered to be the most important, it is natural that the bachelor appears to be immoral and rebellious because of his mischievousness: he tells the three children a story which contains violence, challenges a woman in front of her own niece and nephew and makes her appear stupid. However, his immorality and rebellion reveals that he is

individualistic with his own opinions. He is not bound by the limitations of the time period he is living in.

Although the bachelor appears to be immoral and rebellious in the eyes of the Edwardian society, one must acknowledge that the bachelor possesses many qualities. Through his story, the bachelor is attacking arrogant hypocrites like the aunt: he wants to give a lesson to the arrogant aunt. So instead of verbally in conflict with the aunt, he chooses to tell a story which ironically makes fun of the people like her. This shows that the bachelor is very witty and intelligent.

Throughout his storytelling, the bachelor manages to answer all of the children's questions with unconventional answers. Moreover, the story he tells which includes beautiful park where there is no flowers and only pigs are running around shows that his creativity and imagination are beyond expectation. Besides, the reason why the children love his story is because he is very imaginative and creative in telling story. His story shows distinct creativity. "Bertha is good and everybody loves her" is very stereotypical and lacks variety. The bachelor's story is more realistic and life-like which makes it a good story and ranks him as a good storyteller.

He is a good storyteller. He knows how to make good use of "surprise and suspense" to interest his audience. This is evident when one looks at the answers he gives to the children's questions. His answers are surprisingly unconventional and they harmoniously reinforce his story as a whole. For example, the children ask if there are any sheep in the park, he answers "no". When the children ask him again "why", he says that it is because of the dream of the prince's mother in which "the prince would be either killed by a sheep or a clock falling on him". He even adds that "*the prince never keeps a sheep in the part or a clock in the palace*". He also tells them that although there are no sheep in the park, there are "*lots of little pigs running all over the place*." He keeps surprising the children with his imaginative story and his unconventional answers.

The mischievous bachelor is a flat and static character. However, he is a realistic character who has a very strong personality. He has good imagination and is a good storyteller with amazing wit and intelligence. Although he might appear immoral and rebellious, he is free from the conventional social norms and ideas unlike the aunt.

3. 2. 2. The aunt (The antagonist)

The aunt, the antagonist of the story first appears to be a strict woman with only good intentions for the children. She tries her best to keep the children under control but she fails. Again, she challenges the stranger who gives a "rude" comment that she is an "unsuccessful storyteller". However, in the end she fails to prove to the children that she is an "unsuccessful storyteller". However, in the end she fails to prove to the children that she is a better storyteller as the bachelor outsmarts her in the competition. She has a lot of weaknesses that leads to her downfall.

Firstly, she lacks imagination. She tells a very stereotypical story about a good girl. Moreover, she does not manage to give satisfactory answers to the questions asked by the children.

She is orthodox. She loves conventional rules and values of her time. During Edwardian era, it is believed that children must be taught moral lessons strictly and didactically to become good citizens and civilized people even if it means the corporal punishments (www.laura-cenicola.de). In the story, the aunt says that the kind of story the bachelor tells is "a most improper story". Her words "*the effect of years of careful teaching*" makes her seem like a woman who always wants to live and be controlled by rules. She does not think about

the happiness of children. For her it is always about lessons and rules. This explains why most of what she tells children starts with “Don’t”.

She is rather didactic towards the children. She does not think that children can be given opportunity to decide what is good and bad for them. She thinks that it is difficult to tell stories “that children can both understand and appreciate”. Her attitude towards children is rather irritating for the bachelor and for the children too!

Like Bertha in the bachelor’s story, the aunt herself is arrogant and self-righteous. She furiously attacks the bachelor when she is told that she is not a successful storyteller. She even blames children for her states of being unsuccessful storyteller: “it’s a very difficult thing to tell stories children can both understand and appreciate.”

She degrades the ability of children. She does not think the three children understand the adult’s world and she does not seem to believe that children even have that ability. She treats them like mindless little creatures that do not have the ability to think, feel and understand. Her story reveals that she tries to divide the world into two parts: the real world where adults live and dominate and the imaginary world without any bad things she creates for the children. Her perception of how children should be treated is in her opinion “protective” but it crosses the line of the respect that children deserve. The children can sense that their aunt does not think highly of them and that they are not given a chance to explore the world or to express themselves. So the children become rebellious. They give rude comments.

Her intentions are good and she could have told the children brilliant stories herself if she only has the knowledge to fully appreciate the children’s ability to think as an individual. But her self-righteousness blinds her. So she is a character who loves to live by rules. She is rigid and didactic, orthodox and lacks imagination.

4. Analysis of themes

“**The Open Window**” revolves around the conflict between the gullible Mr. Nuttel and the manipulative Vera. The main theme of this story is “**the emptiness of elaborated manners, conventions and extravagant lifestyle of his people**”. Saki satirizes his extravagant but pretentious society in this story. The story takes place in the drawing room in a country house. In the story, the author presents a short even where the people involved are rich, well-mannered and polite. They live in country houses. They speak, act and live according to Edwardian etiquette. Nuttel brings a letter of introduction which is why he calls it a formal visit. In England in those days, in polite society it is a formal way of introducing oneself to bring a letter of introduction and present it to the host when visiting a stranger because letters of this kind served to guarantee that a move to a new house did not isolate someone from the niece. In the same way, Mrs. Sappleton entertains a stranger with a friendly tone. She brings up the news about the popular sports of the time to start a conversation. She appears to be a perfect hostess. Both Framton and Mrs. Sappleton highly respect the conventional social rules and manners of their time. They both try to be perfect Edwardians. Even the manipulative Vera hides her aggression under the mask of politeness and sophistication. In fact Mr. Nuttel and Mrs. Sappleton are the symbols of extravagant Edwardian people. Therefore, Saki makes fun of their exaggerated manners and extravagant society by letting manipulative Vera fool these two.

The story has a sub-theme. The author includes “young lady of fifteen” twice in his description of Vera. The old man Mr. Nuttel and her aunt were fooled by Vera although she is much younger than both of them. It can be assumed that the author ironically satirizes old

people of his time through his story as his story reveals the theme of **“the faultiness of people’s perception that old people are always wiser than younger ones”**

In **“The Storyteller”**, the aunt is a strict woman. She simply wants the best for her nieces and nephew. But she is rather didactic and oppressive towards the children. She seems to believe that children do not think or feel. However, the children are bored with the aunt’s story and her dull and unimaginative answers. They are in conflict with the aunt. So they give rude comments and they rebel. The bachelor, on the other hand, successfully grabs the attention of the children with his creative story. Unlike the aunt, he teaches children a moral lesson while entertaining them. The author’s mockery towards the aunt by her downfall in the story is to make the readers realize that sometimes didacticism is not the best way of upbringing children. Therefore, the story reveals the theme of **“the inadequacy of didacticism”**

This story also shows a sub-theme of how younger generation can outwit the older generation. In the story, if we assume that the bachelor is younger than the aunt, then the aunt is the only old people in the carriage. Yet she is the one who meets her downfall at the end. The bachelor defeats her. The children apparently do not like her story as they call it **“stupidest story”**. This reveals the sub-theme of **“the faultiness of people’s perception that old people are always wiser than younger ones”**

5. Findings and Discussion

In the two stories, the two protagonists, Vera and the bachelor are remarkably distinctive and similar to each other. Both stories are set in the early 20th century; the period still influenced by the 19th century ideas and values. The 19th century was the age where England reached the peak of its glory. Industrial revolution during the 18th century had made the country’s economy boom (Porter, 2008). Therefore, they had been enjoying the wealthy and high social lifestyle for quite a long time. In the period where the social norms are prioritized, both Vera and the bachelor do not submit to the will of their society and its conventions; Vera lies to the old man and her family while the bachelor tells young children a violent story and makes a woman appear ridiculous and stupid. However both do not show malicious intentions. Their mischievousness makes them appear rebellious and immoral. The both have the ability to tell good stories as they both have good imagination and are creative. The only difference between them is the bachelor is not a manipulator like Vera: Vera tells stories to lie and manipulate people for her own amusement while the bachelor tells stories to attack the didactic, arrogant and self-righteous aunt.

The two antagonists have very different personalities. One is nervous, anxious and gullible while the other is rigid, didactic and unimaginative. However, they are both foils who are quite the direct opposite of their protagonists.

Regarding the themes, the two stories have different main themes. **“The Open Window”** revolves around the naive Mr. Nuttel and the manipulative Vera to attack the extravagant lifestyle, elaborated rules and manners of Edwardian society while **“the storyteller”** reveals Saki’s disappointment in people who bring up children with robotic disciplines and unimaginative rules.

However, the similarity is lie in the sub-themes of the story which is **“the faultiness of people’s perception that old people are always wiser than younger ones”**.

6. Conclusion

Both of the two stories written by Saki claim the reaffirmation of values and the necessity of reform. Although they are satires of Edwardian society, they reveal universal and timeless truths about the nature of people.

This thesis is an attempt to investigate the similarities and differences between characters and between themes as the characters and the themes are two important elements to fully understand to be able to fully understand a piece of fictional work. Understanding “characters” and “themes” is central to the comprehension of the whole work.

The researcher hope that this thesis can make the two works which are both satires more comprehensible for learners of English as a foreign language.

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Appendix

“The Open Window”

Word count: 1274

"My aunt will be down presently, Mr. Nuttel," said a very self-possessed young lady of fifteen; "in the meantime you must try and put up with me."

Framton Nuttel endeavoured to say the correct something which should duly flatter the niece of the moment without unduly discounting the aunt that was to come. Privately he doubted more than ever whether these formal visits on a succession of total strangers would do much towards helping the nerve cure which he was supposed to be undergoing.

"I know how it will be," his sister had said when he was preparing to migrate to this rural retreat; "you will bury yourself down there and not speak to a living soul, and your nerves will be worse than ever from moping. I shall just give you letters of introduction to all the people I know there. Some of them, as far as I can remember, were quite nice."

Framton wondered whether Mrs. Sappleton, the lady to whom he was presenting one of the letters of introduction came into the nice division.

"Do you know many of the people round here?" asked the niece, when she judged that they had had sufficient silent communion.

"Hardly a soul," said Framton. "My sister was staying here, at the rectory, you know, some four years ago, and she gave me letters of introduction to some of the people here."

He made the last statement in a tone of distinct regret.

"Then you know practically nothing about my aunt?" pursued the self-possessed young lady.

"Only her name and address," admitted the caller. He was wondering whether Mrs. Sappleton was in the married or widowed state. An undefinable something about the room seemed to suggest masculine habitation.

"Her great tragedy happened just three years ago," said the child; "that would be since your sister's time."

"Her tragedy?" asked Framton; somehow in this restful country spot tragedies seemed out of place.

"You may wonder why we keep that window wide open on an October afternoon," said the niece, indicating a large French window that opened on to a lawn.

"It is quite warm for the time of the year," said Framton; "but has that window got anything to do with the tragedy?"

"Out through that window, three years ago to a day, her husband and her two young brothers went off for their day's shooting. They never came back. In crossing the moor to their favourite snipe-shooting ground they were all three engulfed in a treacherous piece of bog. It had been that dreadful wet summer, you know, and places that were safe in other years gave way suddenly without warning. Their bodies were never recovered. That was the dreadful part of it." Here the child's voice lost its self-possessed note and became falteringly human. "Poor aunt always thinks that they will come back someday, they and the little brown spaniel that was lost with them, and walk in at that window just as they used to do. That is why the window is kept open every evening till it is quite dusk. Poor dear aunt, she has often told me how they went out, her husband with his white waterproof coat over his arm, and Ronnie, her youngest

brother, singing 'Bertie, why do you bound?' as he always did to tease her, because she said it got on her nerves. Do you know, sometimes on still, quiet evenings like this, I almost get a creepy feeling that they will all walk in through that window - "

She broke off with a little shudder. It was a relief to Framton when the aunt bustled into the room with a whirl of apologies for being late in making her appearance.

"I hope Vera has been amusing you?" she said.

"She has been very interesting," said Framton.

"I hope you don't mind the open window," said Mrs. Sappleton briskly; "my husband and brothers will be home directly from shooting, and they always come in this way. They've been out for snipe in the marshes today, so they'll make a fine mess over my poor carpets. So like you menfolk, isn't it?"

She rattled on cheerfully about the shooting and the scarcity of birds, and the prospects for duck in the winter. To Framton it was all purely horrible. He made a desperate but only partially successful effort to turn the talk on to a less ghastly topic, he was conscious that his hostess was giving him only a fragment of her attention, and her eyes were constantly straying past him to the open window and the lawn beyond. It was certainly an unfortunate coincidence that he should have paid his visit on this tragic anniversary.

"The doctors agree in ordering me complete rest, an absence of mental excitement, and avoidance of anything in the nature of violent physical exercise," announced Framton, who laboured under the tolerably widespread delusion that total strangers and chance acquaintances are hungry for the least detail of one's ailments and infirmities, their cause and cure. "On the matter of diet they are not so much in agreement," he continued.

"No?" said Mrs. Sappleton, in a voice which only replaced a yawn at the last moment. Then she suddenly brightened into alert attention - but not to what Framton was saying.

"Here they are at last!" she cried. "Just in time for tea, and don't they look as if they were muddy up to the eyes!"

Framton shivered slightly and turned towards the niece with a look intended to convey sympathetic comprehension. The child was staring out through the open window with a dazed horror in her eyes. In a chill shock of nameless fear Framton swung round in his seat and looked in the same direction.

In the deepening twilight three figures were walking across the lawn towards the window, they all carried guns under their arms, and one of them was additionally burdened with a white coat hung over his shoulders. A tired brown spaniel kept close at their heels. Noiselessly they neared the house, and then a hoarse young voice chanted out of the dusk: "I said, Bertie, why do you bound?"

Framton grabbed wildly at his stick and hat; the hall door, the gravel drive, and the front gate were dimly noted stages in his headlong retreat. A cyclist coming along the road had to run into the hedge to avoid imminent collision.

"Here we are, my dear," said the bearer of the white mackintosh, coming in through the window, "fairly muddy, but most of it's dry. Who was that who bolted out as we came up?"

"A most extraordinary man, a Mr. Nuttel," said Mrs. Sappleton; "could only talk about his illnesses, and dashed off without a word of goodby or apology when you arrived. One would think he had seen a ghost."

"I expect it was the spaniel," said the niece calmly; "he told me he had a horror of dogs. He was once hunted into a cemetery somewhere on the banks of the Ganges by a pack of pariah dogs, and had to spend the night in a newly dug grave with the creatures snarling and grinning and foaming just above him. Enough to make anyone lose their nerve."

Romance at short notice was her speciality.

“The Storyteller”

Word Count: 2109

It was a hot afternoon, and the railway carriage was correspondingly sultry, and the next stop was at Templecombe, nearly an hour ahead. The occupants of the carriage were a small girl, and a smaller girl, and a small boy. An aunt belonging to the children occupied one corner seat, and the further corner seat on the opposite side was occupied by a bachelor who was a stranger to their party, but the small girls and the small boy emphatically occupied the compartment. Both the aunt and the children were conversational in a limited, persistent way, reminding one of the attentions of a housefly that refuses to be discouraged. Most of the aunt's remarks seemed to begin with "Don't," and nearly all of the children's remarks began with "Why?" The bachelor said nothing out loud. "Don't, Cyril, don't," exclaimed the aunt, as the small boy began smacking the cushions of the seat, producing a cloud of dust at each blow.

"Come and look out of the window," she added.

The child moved reluctantly to the window. "Why are those sheep being driven out of that field?" he asked.

"I expect they are being driven to another field where there is more grass," said the aunt weakly.

"But there is lots of grass in that field," protested the boy; "there's nothing else but grass there. Aunt, there's lots of grass in that field."

"Perhaps the grass in the other field is better," suggested the aunt fatuously.

"Why is it better?" came the swift, inevitable question.

"Oh, look at those cows!" exclaimed the aunt. Nearly every field along the line had contained cows or bullocks, but she spoke as though she were drawing attention to a rarity.

"Why is the grass in the other field better?" persisted Cyril.

The frown on the bachelor's face was deepening to a scowl. He was a hard, unsympathetic man, the aunt decided in her mind. She was utterly unable to come to any satisfactory decision about the grass in the other field.

The smaller girl created a diversion by beginning to recite "On the Road to Mandalay." She only knew the first line, but she put her limited knowledge to the fullest possible use. She repeated the line over and over again in a dreamy but resolute and very audible voice; it seemed to the bachelor as though some one had had a bet with her that she could not repeat the line aloud two thousand times without stopping. Whoever it was who had made the wager was likely to lose his bet.

"Come over here and listen to a story," said the aunt, when the bachelor had looked twice at her and once at the communication cord.

The children moved listlessly towards the aunt's end of the carriage. Evidently her reputation as a story-teller did not rank high in their estimation.

In a low, confidential voice, interrupted at frequent intervals by loud, petulant questionings from her listeners, she began an unenterprising and deplorably uninteresting story about a little girl who was good, and made friends with every one on account of her goodness, and was finally saved from a mad bull by a number of rescuers who admired her moral character.

"Wouldn't they have saved her if she hadn't been good?" demanded the bigger of the small girls. It was exactly the question that the bachelor had wanted to ask.

"Well, yes," admitted the aunt lamely, "but I don't think they would have run quite so fast to her help if they had not liked her so much."

"It's the stupidest story I've ever heard," said the bigger of the small girls, with immense conviction.

"I didn't listen after the first bit, it was so stupid," said Cyril.

The smaller girl made no actual comment on the story, but she had long ago recommenced a murmured repetition of her favourite line.

"You don't seem to be a success as a story-teller," said the bachelor suddenly from his corner.

The aunt bristled in instant defence at this unexpected attack.

"It's a very difficult thing to tell stories that children can both understand and appreciate," she said stiffly.

"I don't agree with you," said the bachelor.

"Perhaps you would like to tell them a story," was the aunt's retort.

"Tell us a story," demanded the bigger of the small girls.

"Once upon a time," began the bachelor, "there was a little girl called Bertha, who was extraordinarily good."

The children's momentarily-aroused interest began at once to flicker; all stories seemed dreadfully alike, no matter who told them.

"She did all that she was told, she was always truthful, she kept her clothes clean, ate milk puddings as though they were jam tarts, learned her lessons perfectly, and was polite in her manners."

"Was she pretty?" asked the bigger of the small girls.

"Not as pretty as any of you," said the bachelor, "but she was horribly good."

There was a wave of reaction in favour of the story; the word horrible in connection with goodness was a novelty that commended itself. It seemed to introduce a ring of truth that was absent from the aunt's tales of infant life.

"She was so good," continued the bachelor, "that she won several medals for goodness, which she always wore, pinned on to her dress. There was a medal for obedience, another medal for punctuality, and a third for good behaviour. They were large metal medals and they clicked against one another as she walked. No other child in the town where she lived had as many as three medals, so everybody knew that she must be an extra good child."

"Horribly good," quoted Cyril.

"Everybody talked about her goodness, and the Prince of the country got to hear about it, and he said that as she was so very good she might be allowed once a week to walk in his park,

which was just outside the town. It was a beautiful park, and no children were ever allowed in it, so it was a great honour for Bertha to be allowed to go there."

"Were there any sheep in the park?" demanded Cyril.

"No;" said the bachelor, "there were no sheep."

"Why weren't there any sheep?" came the inevitable question arising out of that answer.

The aunt permitted herself a smile, which might almost have been described as a grin.

"There were no sheep in the park," said the bachelor, "because the Prince's mother had once had a dream that her son would either be killed by a sheep or else by a clock falling on him. For that reason the Prince never kept a sheep in his park or a clock in his palace."

The aunt suppressed a gasp of admiration.

"Was the Prince killed by a sheep or by a clock?" asked Cyril.

"He is still alive, so we can't tell whether the dream will come true," said the bachelor unconcernedly; "anyway, there were no sheep in the park, but there were lots of little pigs running all over the place."

"What colour were they?"

"Black with white faces, white with black spots, black all over, grey with white patches, and some were white all over."

The storyteller paused to let a full idea of the park's treasures sink into the children's imaginations; then he resumed:

"Bertha was rather sorry to find that there were no flowers in the park. She had promised her aunts, with tears in her eyes, that she would not pick any of the kind Prince's flowers, and she had meant to keep her promise, so of course it made her feel silly to find that there were no flowers to pick."

"Why weren't there any flowers?"

"Because the pigs had eaten them all," said the bachelor promptly. "The gardeners had told the Prince that you couldn't have pigs and flowers, so he decided to have pigs and no flowers."

There was a murmur of approval at the excellence of the Prince's decision; so many people would have decided the other way.

"There were lots of other delightful things in the park. There were ponds with gold and blue and green fish in them, and trees with beautiful parrots that said clever things at a moment's notice, and humming birds that hummed all the popular tunes of the day. Bertha walked up and down and enjoyed herself immensely, and thought to herself: 'If I were not so extraordinarily good I should not have been allowed to come into this beautiful park and enjoy all that there is to be seen in it,' and her three medals clinked against one another as she walked and helped to remind her how very good she really was. Just then an enormous wolf came prowling into the park to see if it could catch a fat little pig for its supper."

"What colour was it?" asked the children, amid an immediate quickening of interest.

"Mud-colour all over, with a black tongue and pale grey eyes that gleamed with unspeakable ferocity. The first thing that it saw in the park was Bertha; her pinafore was so spotlessly white and clean that it could be seen from a great distance. Bertha saw the wolf and saw that it was stealing towards her, and she began to wish that she had never been allowed to come into the park. She ran as hard as she could, and the wolf came after her with huge leaps and bounds.

She managed to reach a shrubbery of myrtle bushes and she hid herself in one of the thickest of the bushes. The wolf came sniffing among the branches, its black tongue lolling out of its mouth and its pale grey eyes glaring with rage. Bertha was terribly frightened, and thought to herself: 'If I had not been so extraordinarily good I should have been safe in the town at this moment.' However, the scent of the myrtle was so strong that the wolf could not sniff out where Bertha was hiding, and the bushes were so thick that he might have hunted about in them for a long time without catching sight of her, so he thought he might as well go off and catch a little pig instead. Bertha was trembling very much at having the wolf prowling and sniffing so near her, and as she trembled the medal for obedience clinked against the medals for good conduct and punctuality. The wolf was just moving away when he heard the sound of the medals clinking and stopped to listen; they clinked again in a bush quite near him. He dashed into the bush, his pale grey eyes gleaming with ferocity and triumph, and dragged Bertha out and devoured her to the last morsel. All that was left of her were her shoes, bits of clothing, and the three medals for goodness."

"Were any of the little pigs killed?"

"No, they all escaped."

"The story began badly," said the smaller of the small girls, "but it had a beautiful ending."

"It is the most beautiful story that I ever heard," said the bigger of the small girls, with immense decision.

"It is the only beautiful story I have ever heard," said Cyril.

A dissentient opinion came from the aunt.

"A most improper story to tell to young children! You have undermined the effect of years of careful teaching."

"At any rate," said the bachelor, collecting his belongings preparatory to leaving the carriage, "I kept them quiet for ten minutes, which was more than you were able to do."

"Unhappy woman!" he observed to himself as he walked down the platform of Templecombe station; "for the next six months or so those children will assail her in public with demands for an improper story!"